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Revisiting the production of L(+)-lactic acid from vine shoots: Bioconversion improvements by employing thermotolerant bacteria.

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Abstract

Vine shoots (*Vitis vinifera* L.) constitute an abundant lignocellulosic source which is frequently underutilised. Alkaline and acidic pretreatments (with and without washing steps) were compared and optimised to release fermentable sugars from vine shoots. An acidic pretreatment using 1.72% H₂SO₄ at 134 °C for 17 min, followed by an enzymatic hydrolysis, offered the most cost-effective results, releasing 40.21 g/L sugars. Three thermotolerant strains, namely *Bacillus coagulans* DSM 2314, *Geobacillus stearothermophilus* DSM 2313 and *G. stearothermophilus* DSM 494, were assessed to produce lactic acid from vine-shoot hydrolysates under aerobic and non-sterile conditions, without the need of detoxification steps. In addition, wine lees were satisfactorily employed as nitrogen sources for the fermentation; providing similar results to yeast extract and being the only nutrient added to vine-shoot hydrolysates. Under optimal conditions, *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 produced 29.21 ± 0.23 g/L lactic acid in 24 h, with a sugar consumption of 98.74 ± 0.07 % and a yield of 96.38 ± 0.76 %, when supplemented with red wine lees. The purity of the isomer L(+) reached 97.59 ± 1.35 % of the total lactic acid produced. Although *G. stearothermophilus* was able to transform the hexoses from vine-shoot hydrolysates into lactic acid, it proved to be inefficient for metabolising pentoses, thus obtaining lower lactic acid values (16-18 g/L).

Keywords: *Bacillus coagulans*; thermotolerance; biorefinery; winery wastes; wine lees.

INTRODUCTION

In the current challenging environmental context, the necessity of developing new alternatives to conventional petrochemical-based plastics enhances the production of biomolecules that act as the building blocks needed to polymerise biodegradable replacements. One of the most promising polymers corresponds to polylactic acid, which is manufactured through the following three stages: lactic acid production, lactic acid purification followed by lactide production and, finally, the polymer synthesis by polycondensation and ring-opening polymerisation routes (Hu et al. 2016; Nduko and Taguchi 2021). In addition, lactic acid, especially the L(+)-lactic acid isomer, has many applications in the food, cosmetic, pharmaceutical and chemical industries (Ajala et al. 2020).

Regarding the first step of the process, the bioproduction of L(+)-lactic acid by microbial fermentation represents a feasible and preponderant method over the chemical synthesis from hydrocarbon sources (Rawoof et al. 2021). However, the production of this chemical compound faces a series of challenges, being the cost of the raw material one of the most predominant since it accounts for up to 70% of the total production cost (Ajala et al. 2020).

To cope with this problem, using the inedible and abundant lignocellulosic feedstocks as a source of carbohydrates for microbial fermentation becomes an essential solution (Nduko and Taguchi 2021). On the other hand, the use of lignocellulosic feedstocks implies several drawbacks mainly associated with their complex and recalcitrant nature, such as the high cost of their pretreatment and hydrolysis process to release fermentable sugars, as well as the simultaneous production of harmful compounds that could inhibit or reduce the microbial productivity of lactic acid (Ajala et al. 2020).

Reduction of the costs associated with lignocellulosic material could be implemented in all the steps of the bioconversion process. For example, at the fermentation stage, the use of thermotolerant bacterial species for lactic acid production could contribute to economic savings related to refrigeration costs, lower risks of microbial contamination, higher yields and greater ease of performing simultaneous saccharification and fermentation (Poudel et al. 2016).

Lactic acid bioproduction from lignocellulosic biomass has been extensively reviewed in the last decades, but works were mainly focused on the

order of Lactobacillales (Abdel-Rahman et al. 2011; Castillo-Martínez et al. 2013; Cubas-Cano et al. 2018; John et al. 2007, 2009; Tarraran and Mazzoli 2018; Wang et al. 2015). However, comparatively, the information on thermophilic species producing lactic acid, such as *Bacillus coagulans* and *Geobacillus stearothermophilus*, is scarce.

Vine shoots (*Vitis vinifera* L.) are the most abundant by-product from the winery industry, representing 93% of the solid residues, and they are generated at a rate of 1.4-2.0 ton/ha; therefore, vast amounts of this lignocellulosic feedstock are produced annually in those countries devoted to viticulture, considering that a total of 7,450,000 ha were under vines worldwide in 2018 (Garita-Cambronero et al. 2021). Production of lactic acid from vine shoots was demonstrated in previous works by using various Lactobacilli species with a final concentration that ranged from 15 g/L to 40 g/L depending on the bacterial species used, the vine shoot pretreatment method selected and the type of fermentation (Nanni et al. 2021).

In this paper, we revisit the production of L(+)-lactic acid using vine shoots as a feedstock in order to improve the previous fermentative processes by using thermotolerant species like *B. coagulans* and *G. stearothermophilus* as a procedure to reduce operational costs associated with detoxification during the production of vine-shoot hydrolysates as well as to avoid sterile and anaerobic conditions during their bioconversion. Besides, the use of wine lees as an alternative source of nitrogen and micronutrients under the thermophilic conditions assayed was also evaluated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Description of vine shoots

Vine shoots (pruning residues) were collected at the experimental plots of ITACyL (Finca Zamadueñas, Valladolid, Spain) in May 2019. These winery by-products were dried in an oven at 45 °C for 48 h (until constant weight), ground in a SM100 Comfort rotary mill (Retsch GmbH, Haan, Germany) and sieved to a size of 0.5-1.0 mm. Dry vine shoots were composed of 32.77% glucan, 11.31% hemicellulose (49.27% total carbohydrates), 2.82% galacturonic acid, 21.30% acid-insoluble lignin, 4.34% protein, 0.52% fat, 7.91% moisture, 2.40% ashes and 13.3 mg/g total phenolic compounds. Chemical characterisation was

performed according to Garita-Cambronero et al. (2021).

Description and processing of wine lees

White wine lees and red wine lees were collected in September-November 2020 at the Oenological Station of Castile and Leon - ITACyL (Rueda, Spain). White wine lees had a density of 1.03 g/L and contained 81.8 g/L ethanol, 6.8 g/L total Kjeldahl nitrogen and 0.43 g/L total phenolic compounds. Red wine lees had a density of 1.05 g/L and contained 99.3 g/L ethanol, 12.2 g/L total Kjeldahl nitrogen and 1.51 g/L total phenolic compounds. Their chemical composition in terms of anions and cations is provided elsewhere (Hijosa-Valsero et al. 2021).

In order to use wine lees as nitrogen sources for microbial fermentation, they were concentrated and sonicated by modifying previously described methods (Bustos et al. 2004a; del Fresno et al. 2019). Briefly, wine lees were centrifuged at 4000 rpm and 4 °C for 15 min with a Fisherbrand GT 4R centrifuge (Thermo Electron LED GmbH, Osterode am Harz, Germany). The supernatant was discarded and replaced by distilled water, the sample was homogenised by shaking and it was centrifuged again. This washing/centrifuging step was performed four consecutive times. Finally, the supernatant was discarded and the decanted solid was sterilised at 121 °C for 15 min. Concentrated wine lees were kept at 4 °C until further use. This solid concentrate contained 23.2 g/kg of total nitrogen (TN) in the case of white wine lees and 18.6 g TN/kg in the case of red wine lees. Then, fermentation broths were supplemented with concentrated wine lees in an amount equivalent to 1.1 g TN/L, and they were sonicated for 30 min at 330 W and 80 kHz in an Elmasonic P 180 H ultrasound bath (Elma Schmidbauer GmbH, Singen, Germany) in 500 mL Erlenmeyer flasks before microbial inoculation (see section *Use of alternative nitrogen sources: wine lees* for more details).

Pretreatment of vine shoots

Two different physicochemical pretreatment methods were assessed for vine shoots, namely, an alkaline pretreatment and an acidic pretreatment. The alkaline pretreatment consisted of treating vine shoots with an aqueous solution of 1.16% NaOH (w/w), at 125 °C for 110 min, as optimised in a previous work (Garita-Cambronero et al. 2021). On

the other hand, the acidic pretreatment employed H₂SO₄ and its working conditions were optimised according to section *Optimisation of the acid pretreatment*. Both pretreatments were performed with a high-pressure 2-L reactor made of alloy Carpenter-20 (Parr Instrument Company, Moline, IL, USA) with a solid-to-solvent ratio of 10% (w/w). In both pretreatments, forty grammes of dry vine shoots were placed in the reactor container and 360 g of the corresponding acidic or alkaline aqueous solution were added. The reaction mixture was heated at a rate of about 7.6 °C/min with continuous stirring, until the programmed working temperature was attained. Then, the reactor was kept at that temperature during the required time for each experiment. Time zero was considered at the beginning of the isothermal stage. At the end of the process, the reactor was cooled and the solid/liquid mixture was recovered.

Optimisation of the acid pretreatment

The conditions of this physicochemical pretreatment were optimised in order to obtain a fermentation broth with the maximum concentration of simple sugars (cellobiose, glucose, xylose, rhamnose and arabinose) and the minimum concentration of inhibitors (formic acid, acetic acid, levulinic acid, furfural, 5-hydroxymethyl furfural and phenolic compounds). In the case of vine shoots, the variables to be optimised were H₂SO₄ concentration (range of 0-3 % w/w), temperature (range of 100-180 °C) and treatment time (range of 2-30 min). A Box-Behnken design and its related response surface methodology (RSM) experiments were performed for the physicochemical treatments; with 3 factors, 15 runs, 1 block and 3 central points. A response surface was calculated and the resulting equations were used to estimate the optimal temperature, time and sulphuric acid concentration values to obtain the highest amount of total sugars released and the lowest amount of total inhibitors in the broth after the physicochemical treatment in the reactor and the subsequent enzymatic hydrolysis. Afterwards, the mathematically estimated optimal points were validated with experiments.

Enzymatic hydrolysis of acid-pretreated samples

After the physicochemical pretreatment, an enzymatic hydrolysis with Cellic CTec 2 at 50 °C was performed for 48 h on the biomass solid/liquid mixture obtained in the reactor, following the

method described by Hijosa-Valsero et al. (2017). For all the experiments leading to the optimisation of the acid pretreatment, an enzymatic dose of 3.60 FPU/g biomass was employed (sections *Optimisation of the acid pretreatment* and *Establishment of optimal conditions for the acidic pretreatment*). However, it was later observed that this dose was insufficient and, for fermentation experiments, this value was increased to 17.40 FPU/g, as suggested by Garita-Cambronero et al. (2021). After enzymatic hydrolysis, vine-shoot hydrolysates were vacuum-filtered (filter paper No. 1305, Filtros Anoa SA, Barcelona, Spain).

Enzymatic hydrolysis of alkali-pretreated samples

The solid/liquid mixture from the pretreatment reactor was centrifuged in order to separate the solid and the liquid fraction. The solid fraction was washed several consecutive times with distilled water until the pH of the rinse water was approximately 7.0. Then, the sample was centrifuged again, the solids were recovered by filtration and a volume of water equivalent to that of the liquid fraction removed was added to the solids. This mixture was subjected to hydrolysis with Cellic CTec 2 with an enzymatic load of 17.40 FPU/g pretreated solids at 50°C and pH 5.0 (citrate buffer 50 mM) for 48 h (Garita-Cambronero et al. 2021). Then, hydrolysates were vacuum-filtered (filter paper No. 1305, 73 g/m², Filtros Anoa SA, Barcelona, Spain). A control experiment without biomass washing before enzymatic hydrolysis was also performed.

Cell growth and inocula preparation

The strains *Bacillus coagulans* DSM 2314, *Geobacillus stearothermophilus* DSM 2313 and *G. stearothermophilus* DSM 494 were purchased from Deutsche Sammlung von Mikroorganismen und Zellkulturen (Braunschweig, Germany). Lyophilised cells of *B. coagulans* were resuspended in 10 mL sterile medium containing Man-Rogosa-Sharpe (MRS) broth (Fisher Scientific SL, Madrid, Spain) and then added to 50 mL MRS medium in glass bottles capped with a rubber septum, where they were incubated at 52 °C. The lyophilised cells of *G. stearothermophilus* strains were reactivated in nutrient broth according to Smerilli et al. (2015) and incubated at 60 °C. After a 24-h incubation, 1.5 mL of each strain were transferred to a sterile cryogenic vial and 0.4 mL glycerol (80 % v/v) were added. The

vials were closed, shaken and stored at -80 °C until being used.

For inocula preparation, a loopful of the thawed glycerinate was added to 50 mL of liquid MRS medium for *B. coagulans* or 50 mL of tryptic soy broth (Becton, Dickinson and Company; Le Pont de Claix, France) for *G. stearothermophilus*. The media were placed in glass bottles capped with a rubber septum and were incubated for 24 h at 100 rpm at 52 °C (*B. coagulans*) or 60 °C (*G. stearothermophilus*) in an Infors HT Ecotron orbital shaker (Infors AG, Bottmingen, Switzerland) until an approximate bacterial density of 5 x 10⁸ cells/mL was attained.

Fermentation tests for different biomass pretreatment methods

The three different vine-shoot hydrolysates described in sections *Enzymatic hydrolysis of acid-pretreated samples* and *Enzymatic hydrolysis of alkali-pretreated samples* (alkaline washed, alkaline non-washed and acidic) were supplemented with 10 g/L yeast extract and their pH was adjusted to 6.0 with concentrated HCl or NaOH aqueous solutions. No sterilisation was applied to fermentation broths. Then, 10 mL inoculum of *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 were added to 100 mL of each type of hydrolysate. Only this bacterial strain was tested in this preliminary experiment because *B. coagulans* has been reported to cope with several lignocellulosic hydrolysates (Poudel et al. 2016), which might guarantee a successful lactic acid production with at least one of the vine-shoot hydrolysates. Fermentations were performed at 50 °C and 200 rpm in a Carousel 6 Plus Reaction Station (Radleys, Essex, United Kingdom), where pH was maintained at 6.0 with an automatic dispenser loaded with an aqueous solution of NaOH 5 M. These experiments were performed in triplicate. The most cost-effective pretreatment method was chosen for further experiments.

Strain comparison

In order to select the most efficient strain for lactic acid production, the strains *B. coagulans* DSM 2314, *G. stearothermophilus* DSM 2313 and *G. stearothermophilus* DSM 494 were compared to ferment the most adequate hydrolysate resulting from the test described in section *Fermentation tests for different biomass pretreatment methods*. Vine-shoot acidic hydrolysates were supplemented with 10 g/L yeast extract and their initial pH was adjusted

to 6.0 for DSM 2314 or to pH 7.0 for DSM 2313 and DSM 494. No sterilisation was applied to fermentation broths. Then, 10 mL of the respective inoculum were added to 100 mL of acidic hydrolysate. Fermentations were performed at 50 °C for *B. coagulans* or 60 °C for *G. stearothermophilus* in a Carousel 6 Plus Reaction Station at 200 rpm, where pH was maintained at 6.0 (*B. coagulans*) or 7.0 (*G. stearothermophilus* strains) with an automatic dispenser loaded with NaOH 5 M. In addition, fermentation controls for each strain were prepared with aqueous solutions containing glucose and xylose mixtures at similar concentrations to those of vine-shoot acidic hydrolysates (22 g/L glucose and 14 g/L xylose), and supplemented with 10 g/L yeast extract. All experiments were performed in triplicate.

Use of alternative nitrogen sources: wine lees

After selecting the most proficient lactic acid-producing strain on acidic vine-shoot hydrolysate, concentrated white and red wine lees were tested as alternative nitrogen sources in comparison to yeast extract. Commercial yeast extract (Fluka, Sigma-Aldrich, Buchs, Switzerland) contained 110 g TN/kg. Yeast extract and concentrated wine lees were added to fermentation broths in such an amount that TN concentrations were always 1.1 g/L. Therefore, for fermentation tests, acidic vine-shoot hydrolysates were supplemented with 10 g/L yeast extract, 47.5 g/L white wine lees or 59.0 g/L red wine lees. In the case of concentrated wine lees, samples were sonicated as explained in section *Description and processing of wine lees*. No sterilisation was applied to fermentation broths. Then, 10 mL inoculum of *B. coagulans* DSM 2134 were added to 100 mL of each type of hydrolysate and fermentations were carried out as described in section *Fermentation tests for different biomass pretreatment methods*.

Chemical analyses

Hydrolysates and fermentation aqueous samples were centrifuged at 13,400 x g in a microcentrifuge for 3 min (Minispin, Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany). The supernatant was filtered through a nylon syringe filter (0.20 µm pore; Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) prior to analysis. Cellobiose, glucose, xylose, rhamnose, arabinose, formic acid, acetic acid, levulinic acid, lactic acid, ethanol, 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (5-HMF) and furfural were quantified by HPLC-RID as described elsewhere (Diez-Antolínez et al. 2018; Paniagua-García et al.

2018). Total phenolic compounds were analysed according to Folin and Denis (1912) and were expressed as gallic acid equivalents (GAE).

Lactic acid isomers were determined by HPLC-DAD with an Agilent 1100 series HPLC system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with a G1315B diode array detector (DAD) monitoring at 254 nm. The separation was carried out with a Chirex® 3126 (D)-penicillamine (150 x 4.6 mm) column and a Chirex® 3126 (D)-penicillamine (30 x 4.6 mm) guard column (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) operated at 30 °C. The mobile phase was an aqueous solution of 0.25 g/L CuSO₄·5H₂O and the flow rate was 1 mL/min. The injection volume was 20 µL and the run time was 30 min.

Hexose consumption (ΔH), pentose consumption (ΔP) and total sugar consumption (ΔS) during the fermentation process were expressed as a percentage. Lactic acid yield, Y (%), was calculated as the ratio between the mass of lactic acid produced (g) and the mass of total sugars consumed (g). In both cases, volumetric corrections due to the addition of NaOH-solution for pH control were performed. Lactic acid productivity, W [g/(L·h)], was calculated as the concentration of lactic acid in the final broth (g/L) divided by the fermentation time (h).

Statistics

Comparisons among samples were assessed with a one-way ANOVA and Tukey's HSD test using the software Statistica 7 (StatSoft Inc., Tulsa, OK, USA). Box-Behnken RSM experimental designs were performed with the software Minitab 16 (Minitab Inc., State College, PA, USA).

RESULTS

Establishment of optimal conditions for the acidic pretreatment

The operational conditions of the physicochemical pretreatment of vine shoots (temperature, time and concentration of H₂SO₄) were optimised with an RSM experimental design focused on maximum sugar release and minimum generation of fermentation inhibitors. Under the RSM-tested conditions, total sugar concentrations ranged between 12.19 and 31.03 g/L (Appendix, Table A1), which represents a sugar recovery efficiency of only 22.58-52.81%, taking into account the initial carbohydrate composition of vine shoots. The data from Table A1

were used to calculate mathematical models to estimate the concentration of each response variable from any combination of the three independent variables (Tables A2-A5). Contour plots for total sugar and inhibitor concentrations are given in Fig. A1 (Appendix).

The mathematical model determined that a pretreatment performed at 134 °C, for 17 min and with a concentration of 1.72% H₂SO₄ (w/w) would produce a hydrolysate containing 30.15 g/L sugars, 0.13 g/L formic acid, 3.90 g/L acetic acid, 0.21 g/L levulinic acid, 0.72 g/L 5-HMF, 0.20 g/L furfural and 0.69 g/L phenolic compounds (Table A6). These optimal working conditions were validated experimentally by treating vine shoots at the calculated conditions, followed by an enzymatic hydrolysis with 3.60 FPU/g biomass (Table 1). In general, all the concentrations were similar to those estimated by the model. Under optimal conditions, the physicochemical pretreatment alone produced 27.50 g/L sugars (Table 1). As shown in Table 1, after completion of the enzymatic hydrolysis with 3.60 FPU/g, a final sugar concentration of 31.13 g/L was attained (very close to the mathematically estimated value of 30.15 g/L), which constitutes a sugar recovery of 52.47%, taking into account the carbohydrate composition of vine shoots.

Table 1. Composition of vine-shoot hydrolysates under optimised acid-pretreatment conditions (134 °C, 17 min and 1.72% w/w H₂SO₄). Estimated and experimental values are given. EH: enzymatic hydrolysis.

Concentration (g/L)	Pretreatment	Pretreatment + EH (3.60 FPU/g biomass)		Pretreatment + EH (17.40 FPU/g biomass)
	Experimental validation	Mathematical estimation (RSM)	Experimental validation	Experimental validation
Cellobiose	0.95	-	0.60	2.08
Glucose	11.73	-	15.62	22.43
Xylose	13.55	-	13.85	14.09
Rhamnose	0.36	-	0.29	0.48
Arabinose	0.91	-	0.77	1.13
Total sugars	27.50	30.15	31.13	40.21
Formic acid	0.14	0.13	0.17	0.11
Acetic acid	4.03	3.90	4.07	3.80
Levulinic acid	0.17	0.21	0.16	0.11
5-HMF	0.80	0.72	0.63	0.40
Furfural	0.20	0.20	0.13	0.13
Phenolic compounds	0.76	0.69	0.64	0.60

Due to the poor release of glucose during the enzymatic hydrolysis step, the enzyme dose was increased from 3.60 to 17.40 FPU/g, as explained in section *Enzymatic hydrolysis of acid-pretreated samples*, in order to obtain higher amounts of monosaccharides from pretreated cellulose. Under these conditions, the total concentration of sugars in the hydrolysate reached 40.21 g/L, while keeping similar values of inhibitors (Table 1). This implies a sugar recovery of 74.05% of initial carbohydrates present in raw vine shoots. Accordingly, this sugar-rich hydrolysate was finally employed for lactic acid fermentation tests.

Fermentability of vine-shoot hydrolysates: effect of pretreatment type

Vine shoots were subjected to two physicochemical pretreatments (alkaline and acidic) and a subsequent enzymatic hydrolysis. In the case of the alkaline pretreatment, two different strategies were applied, namely, washing the pretreated solids with distilled water to remove possible inhibitors or using the unwashed solids. In both cases, the solids underwent an enzymatic hydrolysis thereafter. The alkaline washed hydrolysate contained 1.59 g/L cellobiose, 25.74 g/L glucose, 10.68 g/L xylose, (38.01 g/L total sugars), 0.25 g/L acetic acid and 0.24 g/L total phenolic compounds; whereas the alkaline unwashed hydrolysate contained 1.98 g/L cellobiose, 30.17 g/L glucose, 10.58 g/L xylose, 0.09 g/L arabinose (42.82 g/L total sugars), 0.55 g/L formic acid, 2.13 g/L acetic acid and 0.84 g/L total phenolic compounds. On the other hand, the acidic hydrolysate contained 2.08 g/L cellobiose, 22.43 g/L glucose, 14.09 g/L xylose, 0.48 g/L rhamnose, 1.13 g/L arabinose (40.21 g/L total sugars), 0.11 g/L formic acid, 3.80 g/L acetic acid, 0.11 g/L levulinic acid, 0.40 g/L 5-HMF, 0.13 g/L furfural and 0.60 g/L total phenolic compounds (Table 1). According to these results, the three pretreatments offered similar total sugar concentrations (38-43 g/L), but the types of sugars produced by each treatment were slightly different.

The three abovementioned hydrolysates were supplemented with 10 g/L yeast extract and were inoculated with *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 to initially check their fermentability using a known robust and inhibitor-tolerant species (Zhang et al. 2014). After a 24-h fermentation, it was observed that the unwashed alkaline hydrolysate was toxic for microorganisms and thus unsuitable for lactic acid production (Fig. 1), perhaps due to the moderate

concentrations of formic acid (0.55 g/L) and total phenolic compounds (0.84 g/L) in the hydrolysate or to the presence of non-monitored inhibitors. In addition, the detrimental effect of excess Na^+ on the unwashed NaOH-treated biomass cannot be discarded. On the contrary, the washed alkaline hydrolysate and the acidic hydrolysate were successfully fermented by *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 (Fig. 1). In fact, this was reflected in a significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) cell density in the unwashed-alkaline broth (1.13 ± 0.15) in comparison to the washed-alkaline broth (8.27 ± 0.90) or the acidic broth (7.80 ± 1.88 , expressed as $\times 10^8$ cell/mL in all three cases). Consequently, the final concentrations of lactic acid were 31.70 ± 0.06 g/L, 2.32 ± 0.00 g/L and 29.84 ± 0.47 g/L, for washed-alkaline, unwashed-alkaline and acidic pretreatments, respectively. This implies that

the washed alkaline pretreatment was significantly superior ($p < 0.05$) to the rest of pretreatments for lactic acid production (Fig. 1).

In spite of the good results obtained in the fermentation of the hydrolysates from the washed alkaline-treated vine shoots, the washing step is time- and water-consuming. In contrast, the acidic pretreatment did not imply solid/liquid separations or biomass washing, making it a more straightforward process. Therefore, the acid pretreatment was preferred over the alkaline pretreatment to obtain vine-shoot hydrolysates destined for lactic acid production in the subsequent tests.

Fig. 1 Effect of pretreatment type on a 24-h fermentation of vine-shoot hydrolysates with *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 ($n = 3$).

Fig. 2 Fermentative behaviour of different bacterial strains for a) synthetic control medium (22 g/L glucose and 14 g/L xylose), b) acidic hydrolysates of vine shoots ($n = 3$).

Effect of microbial strain on lactic acid production

The behaviour of the thermotolerant strains *B. coagulans* DSM 2314, *G. stearothermophilus* DSM 494 and *G. stearothermophilus* DSM 2313 was studied by employing both synthetic control media and acidic vine-shoot hydrolysates for lactic acid production.

When using control media, all fermentations were finished in 24 h. In this case, *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 obtained 28.16 ± 0.26 g/L lactic acid, which was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than the concentrations attained by both *G. stearothermophilus* strains, which barely reached 14–17 g/L (Fig. 2a). This can be due to the incomplete sugar consumption of DSM 494 and DSM 2313 (about 99% hexoses and 9% pentoses), hence making the fermentation inefficient, in contrast to the complete sugar consumption of *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 (100% hexoses and 100% pentoses). Therefore, *G. stearothermophilus* DSM 494 and DSM 2313 do not seem adapted to xylose consumption, which is translated into lower lactic acid production values.

When fermenting acidic vine-shoot hydrolysates, *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 was also significantly superior ($p < 0.05$) to *G. stearothermophilus* DSM 494 and DSM 2313 for lactic acid production (Fig. 2b), since concentrations of 29.84 ± 0.47 g/L, 18.22 ± 1.69 g/L and 16.29 ± 0.93 g/L were attained, respectively. In addition, both *G. stearothermophilus* strains needed 48 h to finish the fermentation in vine-shoot hydrolysates, as opposed to *B. coagulans* DSM 2314, which only needed 24 h. Remarkably, *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 and *G. stearothermophilus* DSM 494 obtained significantly higher lactic acid

concentrations in vine-shoot hydrolysates than in control media ($p < 0.05$). Moreover, both *G. stearothermophilus* strains (DSM 494 and DSM 2313) consumed significantly larger amounts of pentoses in vine-shoot hydrolysates than in control media ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 was the most appropriate strain for lactic acid production from acidic vine-shoot hydrolysate and it was employed for further fermentation tests.

Influence of the nitrogen source on lactic acid fermentation

After selecting the acidic pretreatment as the best process for sugar release and *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 as the most proficient lactic acid producer, the effect of substituting yeast extract for concentrated white wine lees and concentrated red wine lees (with a dose of 1.1 g/L TN in all cases) was tested.

As shown in Fig. 3, the three nitrogen sources tested resulted in successful fermentations. In fact, there were no significant differences for lactic acid concentrations among the three nitrogen supplements, reaching values of 29.84 ± 0.47 g/L for yeast extract, 29.11 ± 0.23 g/L for white lees and 29.21 ± 0.36 g/L for red lees. The use of wine lees did not increase fermentation times (24 h), which is advantageous from the economic point of view. However, certain fermentation parameters were significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected by the type of nitrogen source used (Table 2), such as cell density and hexose consumption (higher with yeast extract), or pentose consumption, total sugar consumption and lactic acid yield (higher with red lees). In any case, both white lees and red lees were excellent nutritional alternatives to yeast extract for lactic acid fermentation.

Table 2. Fermentation parameters for *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 feeding on acidic vine-shoot hydrolysates supplemented with various nitrogen sources ($n = 3$). Different letters between brackets (a, b, c) indicate the existence of significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between nitrogen sources for a given parameter. Δ H: hexoses consumption; Δ P: pentoses consumption; Δ S: total sugar consumption; W: lactic acid productivity; Y: lactic acid yield.

Nitrogen source	Time (h)	Lactic acid (g/L)	Acetic acid (g/L)*	Formic acid (g/L)	Ethanol (g/L)	Δ H (%)	Δ P (%)	Δ S (%)	W (g/L·h)	Y (%)	Bacterial density, cells/mL ($\times 10^8$)
Yeast extract	24	29.84 ± 0.47 (a)	3.95 ± 0.19 (a)	0.37 ± 0.03 (a)	0.30 ± 0.04 (a)	97.06 ± 0.09 (a)	99.08 ± 1.06 (ab)	98.48 ± 0.37 (a)	1.24 ± 0.02 (a)	92.78 ± 2.69 (a)	7.80 ± 1.88 (a)
White wine lees	24	29.11 ± 0.23 (a)	3.58 ± 0.03 (b)	0.12 ± 0.03 (b)	1.40 ± 0.03 (b)	94.92 ± 0.15 (b)	96.22 ± 2.09 (a)	97.20 ± 0.81 (b)	1.21 ± 0.01 (a)	86.40 ± 0.78 (b)	5.33 ± 0.60 (ab)
Red wine lees	24	29.21 ± 0.36 (a)	3.68 ± 0.02 (ab)	0.29 ± 0.10 (a)	0.56 ± 0.10 (c)	95.33 ± 0.05 (c)	100 ± 0.00 (b)	98.74 ± 0.07 (a)	1.22 ± 0.01 (a)	96.38 ± 0.76 (a)	2.27 ± 0.67 (b)

* Acetic acid was not produced by *B. coagulans*, but it was already present in the hydrolysate before fermentation.

Fig. 3 Effect of different nitrogen sources (1.1 g/L TN) on lactic acid production in a 24-h fermentation of acidic vine-shoot hydrolysates with *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 (n = 3).

The nature of the lactic acid isomers produced by *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 in vine-shoot acidic hydrolysates was analysed. As expected, isomer L(+) was predominant in the fermentation broth of *B. coagulans* DSM 2314, regardless of the nitrogen source, constituting 97.59 ± 1.35 % of the total lactic acid produced. This high purity facilitates the use of the obtained lactic acid for chemical and food applications.

DISCUSSION

Response surface methodology for the optimisation of the acidic pretreatment

The RSM-optimised acid pretreatment alone produced 27.50 g/L sugars (Table 1). This amount is slightly inferior to those of previous works where vine shoots were pretreated with dilute sulfuric acid (3% H₂SO₄, 130 °C, 15 min, biomass load 11% w/w), reporting values of 9-12 g/L glucose, 17-19 g/L xylose, 4-7 g/L arabinose, 4-6 g/L acetic acid (Bustos et al. 2004b, 2005a,b; Moldes et al. 2006, 2007; Vecino et al. 2017). This can be due to the lower acid concentration employed in the present work, aiming at inhibitor reduction. In fact, Bustos et al. (2005b) obtained an acidic vine-shoot hydrolysate containing 32.8 g/L total sugars, 4.0 g/L acetic acid, 0.7 g/L furfural and 0.1 g/L 5-HMF when employing 3% H₂SO₄ in the pretreatment, but there is no information available about the generation of other

potential inhibitors such as formic acid or phenolic compounds.

Regarding the production of total inhibitors according to the RSM model (Fig. A1b), their generation followed a logical pattern: higher temperatures, higher treatment times and higher acid concentrations resulted in the formation of more inhibitors, which is in agreement with previous theoretical findings (Palmqvist and Hahn-Hägerdal 2000). The experimental concentrations of individual inhibitors were similar to those estimated by the model (Table 1). Although the concentration of acetic acid in the hydrolysate was relatively high (~ 4 g/L), this value should not suppose a problem for lactic acid fermentation, since Zhang et al. (2014) demonstrated that the strain *B. coagulans* IPE22 was able to maintain its growth in the presence of individual concentrations of 2 g/L furfural, 2 g/L 5-HMF, 1 g/L formate, 30 g/L acetate, 3 g/L vanillin and 60 g/L sulfate. Therefore, the inhibitor concentrations obtained in this work by RSM optimisation are clearly low and presumably safe for *B. coagulans*.

Pretreatment types

Although the three pretreatments offered similar total sugar concentrations (38-43 g/L), the types of sugars produced by each treatment were slightly different. In fact, the alkaline unwashed pretreatment yielded the highest glucose values, whereas the acidic pretreatment led to the highest values of xylose and arabinose (pentoses). This was expectable

because alkaline pretreatments are usually employed to remove lignin and favour cellulose degradation in order to obtain glucose; while acid pretreatments are known to efficiently hydrolyse hemicellulose, thus releasing its main components, such as xylose, rhamnose, arabinose or acetyl groups (Hendriks and Zeeman 2009). Another remarkable fact is the effect of each pretreatment on inhibitor generation. When comparing both alkaline pretreatments, it can be observed that the washing step removes formic acid, acetic acid and total phenolic compounds to a great extent. As for the acidic treatment, it produced the highest amounts of acetic acid, levulinic acid, 5-HMF and furfural; which is in agreement with the capacity of strong acids to hydrolyse carbohydrate polymers and degrade hexoses and pentoses into inhibitory substances (Palmqvist and Hahn-Hägerdal 2000; Paniagua-García et al. 2019). In any case, it was possible to minimise inhibitor generation during acidic pretreatment thanks to the RSM performed on vine shoots, especially in terms of formic acid (section *Establishment of optimal conditions for the acidic pretreatment*).

The acidic vine-shoot hydrolysate and the washed-alkaline hydrolysate were readily fermentable by *B. coagulans*, in contrast to the unwashed-alkaline hydrolysate, whose fermentation failed. Therefore, it is essential to wash alkaline-treated biomass to avoid toxic effects during lactic acid fermentation with *B. coagulans* DSM 2314. Conversely, it has been reported that a similar alkaline unwashed pretreatment enabled an efficient ABE fermentation of vine-shoot hydrolysates with *Clostridium beijerinckii* CECT 508 (Garita-Cambronero et al. 2021). Bustos et al. (2005b) reported that an alkaline pretreatment of vine shoots (including a washing step), performed at 130 °C with 8 % NaOH and 9 % biomass load for 75 min, resulted in the production of 24.7 g/L lactic acid in a simultaneous saccharification and fermentation (SSF) process with *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*. Those working conditions were more severe than the ones used in the present study (125 °C, 1.16% NaOH, 110 min), but yet led to a lower lactic acid production, since 31.70 ± 0.06 g/L lactic acid were generated in the present work. This evidences the importance of pretreatment optimisation to reduce inhibitor formation, although the use of different bacterial species in both works could have also played a key role. Regarding acidic pretreatments, Moldes et al. (2007) applied a sulfuric-acid treatment to vine shoots (3% H₂SO₄, 130°C, 15 min, 11% solid load) without posterior enzymatic hydrolysis and obtained 19.2 g/L lactic

acid with *Lb. pentosus* CECT 4023 in batch fermentation in 16 h. The inclusion of a detoxification step with CaCO₃ and adequate nutrient addition improved lactic acid production up to 26.5 g/L in a 48-h batch fermentation with *Lb. pentosus* CECT 4023 (Moldes et al. 2006). Accordingly, the RSM strategy applied to vine shoots in the present study to maximise sugar release while minimising inhibitor production proved to be successful, because 29.84 ± 0.47 g/L lactic acid were obtained from the acidic hydrolysate without the need of detoxification steps (Fig. 1).

Microbial strains

Bacillus coagulans is a thermotolerant aerobic or facultative anaerobic microorganism that can metabolise pentose and hexose sugars by the pentose phosphate pathway and the Embden-Meyerhof-Parnas pathway, respectively, producing L(+)-lactic acid with a yield of 1 g/g for xylose and 1 g/g for glucose (Poudel et al. 2016). This species has been efficiently employed for lactic acid production from several food and agriculture by-products, such as organic kitchen waste (Sakai and Ezaki 2006), sugarcane bagasse (van der Pol et al. 2016), *Phragmites australis* biomass (Zhang et al. 2018) or wheat straw (Maas et al. 2008; Zhang et al. 2014), obtaining yields of 0.94-0.98 g/g and lactic acid concentrations in the range of 38-86 g/L depending on the initial sugar concentration.

Geobacillus stearothermophilus is a thermophilic and amyolytic facultatively-anaerobic bacterium which has been reported to produce about 40 g/L lactic acid from substrates containing 50 g/L potato starch under non-sterile conditions, with low nutritional requirements and reaching a complete sugar consumption (Smerilli et al. 2015). Kunasundari et al. (2017) have also described its ability to produce lactic acid from corn waste starch. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that *G. stearothermophilus* is tested for the fermentation of lignocellulosic hydrolysates containing hexoses and pentoses. Although *G. stearothermophilus* has been used to produce cellulase enzymes for cellulose hydrolysis (Alrumman 2016), the present results indicate that it is not an adequate species to deal with hemicellulose or pentoses.

In recent years, different species have been tested for lactic acid production from vine-shoot hydrolysates with variable results (Nanni et al. 2021). For instance, 21.7-24.7 g/L lactic acid have been produced with *Lb. rhamnosus* (Bustos et al. 2005b), 15.6-26.5 g/L with

Lb. pentosus CECT 4023 (Bustos et al. 2004b, 2005a; Moldes et al. 2006, 2007), or 14.3 g/L with *Lactococcus lactis* CECT 4434 (Rodríguez et al. 2010). The highest lactic acid concentration (36.4 g/L) was reported with a coculture of *Lb. pentosus* CECT 4023 and *Lb. plantarum* CECT 221 dealing with a mixture of acidic hydrolysates and alkaline-treated solids, under simultaneous saccharification and fermentation conditions (Rodríguez-Pazo et al. 2013). In all those cases, Lactobacilli had been supplemented with mineral salts (Man-Rogosa-Sharpe or Mercier nutrients) or corn steep liquor, in addition to yeast extract, for the fermentation of vine shoots. It must be noted that only *Lb. rhamnosus* and *Lactococcus lactis* are known to produce isomer L(+) with a high degree of purity, whereas *Lb. pentosus* and *Lb. plantarum* generate a mixture of isomers L(+) and D(-). Accordingly, *B. coagulans* DSM 2314, with a production of about 30 g/L of optically pure L(+)-lactic acid, seems equally or even more efficient for lactic acid production from vine-shoot hydrolysates than previously reported Lactobacilli strains. In addition, its thermotolerance enabled the work under non-sterile conditions during the whole process, which simplifies the operation.

Nitrogen sources

The use of wine lees as nitrogen sources for the fermentation of vine-shoot hydrolysates had been explored previously. However, in those cases, lactic acid production decreased compared to conventional organic nitrogen sources. For instance, Bustos et al. (2005b) worked with *Lb. rhamnosus* and obtained 24.7 g/L lactic acid adding Man-Rogosa-Sharpe nutrients and 21.7 g/L lactic acid adding wine lees. Similarly, Moldes et al. (2007) employed *Lb. pentosus* CECT 4023 and reported 19.2 g/L lactic acid with Mercier nutrients and 15.6 g/L with wine lees. Therefore, *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 seems to utilise wine lees more easily than Lactobacilli, since in the present study its performance was similar when fed with yeast extract or with concentrated wine lees. This is probably related to the ability of *B. coagulans* to grow on media containing inorganic nitrogen and low amounts of organic nitrogen, thus supposing an advantage in comparison to Lactobacillales strains, whose nutritional requirements are more demanding (Poudel et al. 2016).

CONCLUSIONS

Through pretreatment optimisation and strain screening, it was possible to ferment vine-shoot hydrolysates with *B. coagulans* without the need of detoxification steps, yet obtaining higher L(+)-lactic acid concentrations than previously reported with strains of the order Lactobacillales. The use of the thermotolerant bacteria *B. coagulans* implied several advantages, such as working under aerobic and non-sterile conditions or the efficient use of wine lees as single additional nutrient to vine-shoot hydrolysates. This study opens the way to new microbiological processes where other lignocellulosic or agri-food biomasses could be employed as feedstocks for L(+)-lactic acid production.

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<https://biovino.es>

<http://www.agrocycle.eu/>

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APPENDIX

Optimisation of the acidic pretreatment

The conditions of the physicochemical pretreatment were optimised in order to obtain a fermentation broth with the maximum concentration of simple sugars (cellobiose, glucose, xylose, rhamnose and arabinose) and the minimum concentration of inhibitors (formic acid, acetic acid, levulinic acid, furfural, 5-hydroxymethyl furfural and phenolic compounds), with a solid-to-solvent ratio of 10% (w/w). The variables to be optimised were H₂SO₄ concentration (range of 0-3 % w/w), temperature (range of 100-180 °C) and treatment time (range of 2-30 min). A Box-Behnken design and its related response surface methodology (RSM) experiments were performed for the physicochemical treatments; with 3 factors, 15 runs, 1 block and 3 central points (Table A1). Under the RSM-tested conditions, total sugar concentrations ranged between 12.19 and 31.03 g/L (Table A1).

The data from Table A1 were used to calculate mathematical models to estimate the concentration of each response variable from any combination of the three independent variables (Tables A2, A3, A4 and A5). The contour plots for total sugar concentration and inhibitor concentrations are given in Figure A1. The mathematical model determined that a pretreatment performed at 134 °C, for 17 min and with a concentration of 1.72% H₂SO₄ would produce a hydrolysate containing 30.15 g/L sugars, 0.13 g/L formic acid, 3.90 g/L acetic acid, 0.21 g/L levulinic acid, 0.72 g/L 5-HMF, 0.20 g/L furfural and 0.69 g/L phenolic compounds (Table A5). These optimal working conditions were validated experimentally by treating vine shoots at 134 °C, 17 min and 1.72% H₂SO₄, followed by an enzymatic hydrolysis with 3.60 FPU/g biomass.

Table 1 shows the concentrations of sugars and inhibitors generated during the experimental validation of the optimal acidic pretreatment conditions for vine shoots. Under optimal conditions, the physicochemical pretreatment alone produced 27.50 g/L of sugars. As shown in Table 1, after completion of the enzymatic hydrolysis with 3.60 FPU/g, a final sugar concentration of 31.13 g/L was attained (very close to the mathematically estimated value of 30.15 g/L), which constitutes a sugar recovery of only 52.47%, taking into account the carbohydrate composition of vine shoots. Due to the poor release of glucose during the enzymatic hydrolysis step, the enzyme dose was increased from 3.60 to 17.40 FPU/g as explained in section *Enzymatic hydrolysis of acid-pretreated samples*, to obtain higher amounts of monosaccharides from pretreated cellulose. Under these conditions, the total concentration of sugars in the hydrolysate reached 40.21 g/L, while keeping similar values of inhibitors (Table 1). This result implies a sugar recovery of 74.05% of initial carbohydrates present in raw vine shoots.

Table A1. Concentrations of sugars and inhibitors obtained for each of the experimental conditions of the RSM, for the pretreatment of vine shoots.

RSM experiment	Independent variables			Response variables (g/L)*						
	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)	H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	Total sugars	Formic acid	Acetic acid	Levulinic acid	5-HMF	Furfural	Phenolic comp.
1	180	30	1.5	13.79	2.85	4.75	4.94	1.12	3.41	1.43
2	100	30	1.5	18.96	0.06	0.96	0	0.03	0	0.29
3	180	16	0	26.47	0.52	3.75	0.06	0.26	0.15	1.30
4	140	2	0	15.00	0	0.32	0	0	0	0.23
5	140	16	1.5	31.03	0.18	4.02	0.25	0.76	0.3	0.73
6	100	16	0	13.54	0	0.1	0	0	0	0.19
7	180	16	3	12.19	4.16	4.63	7.66	0.59	2.36	1.44
8	180	2	1.5	27.67	0.87	4.65	1.27	0.76	2.13	1.43
9	140	30	0	15.84	0.09	0.4	0	0.02	0	0.50
10	140	16	1.5	30.01	0.19	3.97	0.27	0.74	0.25	0.71
11	140	2	3	28.36	0.13	3.76	0.19	0.61	0.13	0.61
12	140	16	1.5	29.89	0.18	4.03	0.25	0.71	0.24	0.76
13	140	30	3	26.69	0.64	4.39	1.27	0.32	1.16	1.17
14	100	2	1.5	16.42	0	0.35	0	0	0	0.26
15	100	16	3	19.67	0	1.38	0	0.5	0	0.29

(*) Note: These concentrations were measured after the combination of physicochemical and enzymatic hydrolysis (3.60 FPU/g biomass).

Table A2. Estimated regression coefficients of Total Sugars (g/L).

Term	Coefficient	Standard error coef.	T	p
Constant	-109.455	37.1036	-2.950	0.032
Temperature (°C)	1.559	0.5042	3.092	0.027
Time (min)	1.582	0.8489	1.864	0.121
H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	20.442	7.7120	2.651	0.045
Temperature (°C) * Temperature (°C)	-0.005	0.0018	-2.601	0.048
Time (min) * Time (min)	-0.019	0.0143	-1.353	0.234
H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w) * H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	-2.240	1.2479	-1.795	0.133
Temperature (°C) * Time (min)	-0.007	0.0048	-1.522	0.189
Temperature (°C) * H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	-0.085	0.0450	-1.892	0.117
Time (min) * H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	-0.030	0.1285	-0.233	0.825
S = 5.39515	PRESS = 2317.82			
R-square = 78.88%	R-square(pred.) = 0.00%	R-square(adjusted) = 40.87%		

Table A3. Analysis of variance of Total Sugars (g/L).

Source	Df	Sum of squares Seq.	Sum of squares Adjust.	Mean squares Adjust.	F	p
Regression	9	543.623	543.623	60.403	2.08	0.218
Lineal	3	67.372	468.022	156.007	5.36	0.051
Temperature (°C)	1	16.618	278.253	278.253	9.56	0.027
Time (min)	1	18.514	101.142	101.142	3.47	0.121
H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	1	32.240	204.518	204.518	7.03	0.045
Quadratic	3	303.130	303.130	101.043	3.47	0.107
Temperature (°C) * Temperature (°C)	1	166.154	196.898	196.898	6.76	0.048
Time (min) * Time (min)	1	43.185	53.247	53.247	1.83	0.234
H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w) * H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	1	93.791	93.791	93.791	3.22	0.133
Interaction	3	173.121	173.121	57.707	1.98	0.235
Temperature (°C) * Time (min)	1	67.404	67.404	67.404	2.32	0.189
Temperature (°C) * H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	1	104.142	104.142	104.142	3.58	0.117
Time (min) * H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	1	1.575	1.575	1.575	0.05	0.825
Residual error	5	145.538	145.538	29.108		
Lack of fit	3	144.753	144.753	48.251	122.96	0.008
Pure error	2	0.785	0.785	0.392		
Total	14	689.161				

Table A4. Estimated regression coefficients of Total Inhibitors (g/L).

Term	Coefficient	Standard error coef.	T	p
Constant	25.3726	7.08566	3.581	0.016
Temperature (°C)	-0.4085	0.09628	-4.242	0.008
Time (min)	-0.2286	0.16211	-1.410	0.218
H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	-3.8288	1.47276	-2.600	0.048
Temperature (°C) * Temperature (°C)	0.0016	0.00034	4.720	0.005
Time (min) * Time (min)	-0.0042	0.00274	-1.532	0.186
H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w) * H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	-0.6119	0.23831	-2.568	0.050
Temperature (°C) * Time (min)	0.0030	0.00092	3.231	0.023
Temperature (°C) * H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	0.0539	0.00859	6.272	0.002
Time (min) * H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	0.0365	0.02453	1.487	0.197
S = 1.03031	PRESS = 84.8308			
R-square = 99.06%	R-square(pred.) = 84.92%	R-square(adjusted) = 97.36%		

Table A5. Analysis of variance of Total Inhibitors (g/L).

Source	Df	Sum of squares Seq.	Sum of squares Adjust.	Mean squares Adjust.	F	p
Regression	9	557.290	557.290	61.9211	58.33	0.000
Lineal	3	466.227	23.771	7.9237	7.46	0.027
Temperature (°C)	1	339.087	19.106	19.1057	18.00	0.008
Time (min)	1	18.316	2.112	2.1115	1.99	0.218
H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	1	108.824	7.175	7.1746	6.76	0.048
Quadratic	3	35.871	35.871	11.9571	11.26	0.012
Temperature (°C) * Temperature (°C)	1	26.971	23.650	23.6498	22.28	0.005
Time (min) * Time (min)	1	1.900	2.490	2.4901	2.35	0.186
H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w) * H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	1	6.999	6.999	6.9993	6.59	0.050
Interaction	3	55.191	55.191	18.3971	17.33	0.004
Temperature (°C) * Time (min)	1	11.079	11.079	11.0789	10.44	0.023
Temperature (°C) * H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	1	41.764	41.764	41.7639	39.34	0.002
Time (min) * H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	1	2.349	2.349	2.3486	2.21	0.197
Residual error	5	5.308	5.308	1.0615		
Lack of fit	3	5.301	5.301	1.7670	527.50	0.002
Pure error	2	0.007	0.007	0.0033		
Total	14	562.597				

Table A6. Response optimisation for the acidic pretreatment.

Optimisation criteria						
	Goal	Inferior	Objective	Superior	Weighing	Importance
Total sugars (g/l)	Maximum	27.00	32.00	32.00	1	1
Formic acid (g/l)	Minimum	0.10	0.10	0.50	1	1
Acetic acid (g/l)	Minimum	2.00	2.00	4.00	1	1
Levulinic acid (g/l)	Minimum	0.00	0.00	0.27	1	1
5-HMF (g/l)	Minimum	0.25	0.25	0.75	1	1
Furfural (g/l)	Minimum	0.13	0.13	0.30	1	1
Phenolic compounds (g/l)	Minimum	0.60	0.60	1.00	1	1

Local solution:	
Temperature (°C)	= 134.316
Time (min)	= 17.0304
H ₂ SO ₄ (% w/w)	= 1.71819

Estimated responses:		
Total sugars (g/l) = 30.1522	Desirability = 0.630447	
Formic acid (g/l) = 0.1348	Desirability = 0.912902	
Acetic acid (g/l) = 3.8963	Desirability = 0.051837	
Levulinic acid (g/l) = 0.2050	Desirability = 0.240854	
5-HMF (g/l) = 0.7202	Desirability = 0.059656	
Furfural (g/l) = 0.2024	Desirability = 0.573852	
Phenolic compounds (g/l) = 0.6866	Desirability = 0.783442	
Composite desirability = 0.294628		

Figure A1. Contour plots for vine shoot pretreatments in the RSM experimental design. a) Total sugar concentrations. b) Concentration of the sum of inhibitors.